

Paper 5

BEST PRACTICES IN TEACHING, LEARNING AND EVALUATION

Subramanya Bhat*, Shreepathy Ranga Bhatta B. **

*College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangaluru-India

**College of Commerce and Business Management, Srinivas University, Mangaluru-India

Abstract

Teaching, Learning and Evaluation is one of the major criteria while universities are getting accredited by the concern authorities. NAAC has given a weight age of 200 out of 1000 for this specific aspect, and it shows the matter of its significance. Hence universities need to adopt some of the best practices under these criteria. Aspects like Student Satisfaction Survey(SSS) , Student-Teacher Ratio, Retaining Experienced Faculties, Having an Effective Teaching with Learning Management System are the major areas to be addressed. Student Centric Learning Practices like Programs for fast and slow learners, Student Mentor assignments, Measuring the Outcome as well as usefulness of a given course is also some of the issues which needs to be considered. Best practices in Student Evaluation Process and automation of this process is also a matter of concern under these criteria. This paper will discuss some of the best practices adopted in Srinivas University under the NAAC accreditation process.

Keywords: Student Satisfaction Survey; NAAC; Student-Teacher Ratio; Learning Management System; and Student Centric Learning.

1. Introduction

In every walk of life the process of assessment takes place in one or the other form. If the evaluation process is removed from human life then perhaps the aim of life may be vanished. It is only through evaluation that one can differentiate good and bad. The whole sequence of social progress orbits around the evaluation process. In education how much a student has prospered in achieving his aims, can only be realized through evaluation. Hence there is a close relationship between evaluation and aims. In learning, it helps designing objectives, learning experiences and valuation of learner performance. Besides this, it is very worthwhile to bring perfection in teaching and curriculum. It provides accountability to the social order, parents, and to the education system. In brief, evaluation is a central prerequisite for the education system. It fulfills various purposes in any education systems like quality control in education, selection/entrance etc. It also helps one to take decisions about success in specific future activities and offers guidance to further studies and occupation. Some of the educationists view evaluation identical

with that of learner appraisal, but evaluation has an extended role also of questioning or challenging the aims. A simple image explaining the role of evaluation in the teaching-learning process is presented below:

Representation of the Role of Evaluation in the Teaching-Learning Process

About the receiving end in this learning process, student learning is also said to have great influence by the diversity in their background, abilities and other personal attributes.

1.1. About NAAC and its Accreditation

In pursuit of quality in learning process, the National Assessment and Accreditation Council [NAAC], a body that judges and accredits higher education institutions in India, an autonomous body backed by University Grants Commission of Government of India comes to the picture. Imbibing the objectives of quality in higher education NAAC has identified the following seven criteria to serve as the basis of its assessment procedures:

NAAC has identified a set of seven criteria to serve as the basis of its assessment procedures. NAAC has categorized the Higher Educational Institutions into three major types (University, Autonomous College, and Affiliated/Constituent College) and assigned different weightages to these criteria under different key aspects based on the functioning and organizational focus of the three types of HEIs.

Key Indicators and Weightages

The criterion-wise differential weightages for the three types of HEIs are:

Curricular Aspects	150 (U)	150 (Au)	100 (Aff)
Teaching-learning & Evaluation	200 (U)	300 (Au)	350 (Aff)
Research, Innovations & Extension	250 (U)	150 (Au)	120 (Aff)
Infrastructure & Learning Resources	100 (U)	100 (Au)	100 (Aff)
Student Support & Progression	100 (U)	100 (Au)	130 (Aff)
Governance, Leadership & Management	100 (U)	100 (Au)	100 (Aff)
Institutional Values & Best Practices	100 (U)	100 (Au)	100 (Aff)

Key Indicators

Under each Criterion a few Key Indicators are identified, These Key Indicators (KIs) are further delineated as Metrics which actually elicit responses from the HEIs.

Source: <http://naac.gov.in/index.php/assessment-accreditation#process>

The aforesaid seven criteria are further divided into "Key Aspects". These are nothing but important assessment gauges and the Seven Criteria which encompasses them, as probes or leads for the Peer Team members to understand the micro-level quality parameters. These indicators enable the calculating the Key Aspect-wise Grade Points (KA-GPS) and the Criterion-wise score to arrive at the quality status of the institution.

This paper focuses on some of the best practices adopted in Srinivas University with special reference to "The teaching-Learning and Evaluation" parameter considered for the NAAC accreditation process.

1.2. About Srinivas University

The University of Srinivas, Mangalore, is a private research university in Mangalore, Karnataka, India, founded in 2013 by the law of the state of Karnataka. The University of Srinivas is the flagship of a group of institutions from 18 Srinivas, founded by the Sham RAO Foundation, Mangalore, India, which is a private charitable foundation, founded in 1988 by a Certified Accountant A. Raghavendra Rao. A Shama RAO foundation has many vocational colleges in Mangalore, which include Srinivas Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Center, Srinivas Institute of Dental Sciences, Srinivas Institute of Technology, Srinivas College of Pharmacy, Srinivas Institute of Nursing Sciences, A Shama Rao Nursing School, Srinivas Integrated Campus, Srinivas College of Hotel Management, Vijayalakshmi Institute of Hospitality Sciences, Srinivas First Grade College, Srinivas School of Engineering, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas School of Business, Srinivas School of Management, Srinivas College of Education, Srinivas Institute of Social Work.

Currently, the university offers both postgraduate [PG] and undergraduate [UG] programs 8 colleges with about 60 courses. University also has innovative and super specialty program both at UG and at the PG level tuning learners to industrial employability with innovations in the research system by focusing on continuous assessment and making it reliable. The university has established links with many industries, universities and educational service providers to significantly improve the quality and value of courses and degrees, respectively.

2. About teaching-Learning and Evaluation in Srinivas University

Under the Srinivas University, teaching-learning mechanisms of the institution are premeditated aptly for the learner group. The student-centered education through suitable pedagogy helps effective learning. Faculties provide a wide range of learning exposures to students, individually as well as collaboratively. The teachers practice every modality so that the student community feels a sense of responsibility towards their learning and eventually the atmosphere becomes conducive for learning.

Further, to focus on NAAC requirements, the explanation further will orbit around the following “Key Aspects” of assessment as prescribed by the NAAC i.e., criterion 2- Teaching- Learning and Evaluation has following parameters with respective weightage in terms of assessment score;

- | | |
|---|------------|
| 1. Student Enrolment and Profile | - 10 marks |
| 2. Catering to Student Diversity | - 20 marks |
| 3. Teaching- Learning Process | - 20 marks |
| 4. Teacher Profile and Quality | - 50 marks |
| 5. Evaluation Process and Reforms | - 40 marks |
| 6. Student Performance and Learning Outcome | - 30 marks |
| 7. Student Satisfaction Survey | - 30 marks |

3. about the student-centric learning at Srinivas University

In our university, students are taught and fortified to participate in paper presentation/seminars and prepare project proposals and thus carry out the extension of their learning. Students are encouraged to contribute technical articles to develop written skills. Conducting seminars, Guest lectures /conferences so that the students refer more and more study materials, journals and other reference books for seeking extra information. Special focus is also given to individual student through mentors both in academics and co-curricular deeds. Students are induced to apply their acquired knowledge by designing and producing working models and developing software etc. Availability of learning resources through CDs and DVDs, Value added courses; special certificate programs etc. during students' courses tenure help in developing special skill like presentation, communication, interpersonal skills and overall employability as well. We also make students visit industrial establishments on regular basis and

attend occasional special training programs and also assigning mini projects both individually as well as in groups and guiding them in accomplishment of the same.

As a special practice we also follow mentoring process. Here individual faculty is normally allotted 5-10 students (number may vary differ course to course), who are responsible for all activities carried out by the student and they also keep a close supervision by timely mentorship. Regular meetings are conducted by the course coordinators every semester to appraise the result.

4. Student Satisfaction Survey (SSS)

Student Satisfaction Survey Process has the following flow as per the NAAC.

Step-1 Furnishing the student enrolment details in the following format as excel sheet given in portal by ensuring the followings;

- Not to alter column name and order as both are case sensitive;
- Without any repetition Name, e-mail address & mobile number
- Total entries should not be greater than the students marked in for Institutional information for Quality Assessment (IIQA).

Step -2 Institutions simultaneously will be required to do data Validation and verification (DVV Process)

Step-3 NAAC will send the questionnaire with 21 questions (format also given in annexure-1) directly to the students on a random basis with following conditions;

- Maximum of Two survey attempts will be initiated to reach 10% of student population or 500, whichever is lesser.
- If the response rate is lower than the limits mentioned by NAAC, the metric will not be taken up for evaluation.
- SSS will be completed within 30 days simultaneously with data validation and Verification (DVV) process
- As soon as survey is initiated by the co ordinator of NAAC, it has to be completed within 10 days.
- The institute can encourage students to participate in survey and guide them about survey to make the SSS possible within the given time period of 10 days.
- SSS questionnaire is in English. NAAC website will have both versions available. If needed higher education institutions can make local language translation available for information of students before they take the survey.

Step - 4 NAAC closing the web link to fill SSS questionnaire; and will calculate and finalize student survey metric value for the institution.

4.1. Student Satisfaction Survey in Srinivas University

Student Satisfaction Survey is an integral input factor for all policies of the institution. The institution has the mechanism for analysing student feedback on institutional performance. The institution follows the mechanism of collecting feedback from every student (Both PG & UG) before they conclude each semester of respective course. However in pursuit of accreditation, modification in the existing format of feedback system can be made as follows;

Step -1 – Designing a questionnaire imbibing questions as per NAAC (21 question format also given in annexure-1) as well as other questions (Suggestive format given in annexure-2) which is necessary for the reports for NAAC as well as other institutional requirement.

Step – 2 – Assigning a dedicated staff to administer the system who will feed this is Google form or physical form in a questionnaire and circulate to all the students in all course on a regular basis at least once in every year. This has to be a serious task with dedicated efforts to ensure that the responses furnished by students are genuine with empathy towards the institution.

Step – 3 – Analysis of collected feedback by establishing proper analysis frameworks by competent resource people.

Step - 4 – Infer the result to competent appropriate authorities for proper controlling measures if in case found to be exercised.

5. Student Mentor Program (SMP)

The SMP will help mentors develop strong soft skills, as they will be interacting with the 10-12 mentees assigned to them under the SMP. Building a rapport with the students and trying to understand what problems they are suffering from will definitely enhance the communication skills of a mentor. In SU, the SMP has been organised at two to three different levels like, by assigning mentors at course level, class level and also by assigning mentors to a group of 10 to 15 students in each class. The individual mentors will be regularly having a one to one session with each student to know about all aspects of the student in terms of academic performance as well as co-curricular performance. Along with that even their personal problems are also being addressed by the assigned mentors. Later the mentors will be reporting to the class co-ordinators and the same can be conveyed to course co-ordinators.

6. An Outcome based Course Design

Outcome-based education is one of the most significant global developments in recent years education field. In Outcome based education, the major focus must be primarily on two aspects. Firstly the course design needs to orient towards the outcome based and secondly the education delivery process also needs to be outcome oriented. In SU, every course coordinator will take at most precautions while designing the respective course so as to be outcome based. Accordingly latest industry oriented syllabus needs to be included in the curriculum and proper credits will be assigned to each of such course. Each semester has been included with additional 2 non-core subjects like mini projects, Case Study analysis, General and Technical Aptitude, etc. Second major focus must be on delivering these courses to the student community. Hence in SU, the importance is given on hands on implementation of such course contents using computer labs and tools by using appropriate simulation software. Measuring the outcome of such course is really a challenging task and one can evaluate students by using different parameters like mock tests, interviews and even some campus recruitment activities. Students who take such courses can enrol to some certification exams and get themselves certified in respective fields.

7. Student Evaluation Process

Student Evaluation is one of the key activities in any university, and it will carry significant weight age during NAAC grading. By using a set of established criteria aligned with targeted standards/outcomes, it is possible to fairly, consistently, and defensibly make a judgment-based evaluation of students' performances. SU believes in the practice of continues evaluation of a student right from the beginning of

the course till completion of it. Hence here students' performance in each of the courses will be measured by assigning 50% weight age for the internal assessment and 50% for the external examinations. Even the internal performance is evaluated based on overall performance of the students in terms of Internal Exams, Assignments and percentage of attendance. 60% of internal performance is from the internal tests, and 20% will be from the assignment components and rest 20% is from their attendance performance. Even the semester exams are being evaluated by two examiners internal as well as external and the best out of two will be considered with the condition that difference between two should be within 15 marks. To clear any course, a student is required top score 50% of marks both in Internal as well as External marks. It also enforces to get 50% of the total score assigned to each of the courses. SU has the practice of announcing the results within 10 to 15 days from the last day of the examination held. This is according to the best practice required as per the NAAC assessment. SU is using automation of about 50% in the overall student evaluation process and this will be further improved in coming days.

8. Conclusion

As Teaching, Learning and Evaluation are the major criteria while universities are getting accredited by NAAC; SU has implemented some best practices to get better ranking. By adapting to the UGC guidelines, SU has implemented the standard SSS format and evaluated these feed backs from its stake holders. By maintaining a decent Student-Teacher Ratio, SU is trying to get better position during the assessment. Retaining Experienced Faculties, and there by providing Student Centric Learning Practices like Programs for fast and slow learners, Student Mentorship Program(SMP) , are the few best practice used in SU. Designing a Outcome based curriculum and Measuring the Outcome as well as usefulness of a given course will help the institutions to attain high ranks during the accreditation process. Best practices in Student Evaluation Process and automation of this process also a matter of concern, while any institutions are being evaluated.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Prof.V.S.Prasad and Antony Stella (2004) Best Practices in Higher Education for Quality Enhancement: The NAAC, Bangalore.
- [2]. Dr.S.K.Mangal (2001) Educational Technology: Tandon Publications, Ludhiana.
- [3]. E.G. Vedanayagam (1969) Teaching Technology for College Teachers: Sterling Publishers(P) Ltd, New Delhi.
- [4]. P.D. Shukla (1990) The New Education Policy in India: Sterling Publishers (P) Ltd, New Delhi.
- [5]. NAAC News, January 2004, April 2004 and NAAC Decennial special, October 2004.

[6]. College Times, GCTA, September, 2004.

[7]. SSS FAQ's. (2018).Retrieved from <http://www.naac.gov.in/docs/>

[8]. SSS Flowcharts. (2018).Retrieved from <http://www.naac.gov.in/docs/>

[9].NAAC Revised Accreditation Framework.(2018). Retrieved from [http://www.naac.gov.in/docs/Revised%20Accreditation%20Framework%20 \(RAF\).pdf](http://www.naac.gov.in/docs/Revised%20Accreditation%20Framework%20(RAF).pdf)

[10]. Formats, Guidelines and User manuals for Assessment and Accreditation IIQA (Institutional Information for Quality Assessment). (2018).Retrieved from <http://www.naac.gov.in/apply-now>.